

Vegetation composition and natural regeneration dynamics of Sal (*Shorea robusta*) forests: A case study from Rangpur Division, Bangladesh

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Abstract

The overall objectives of the study were to assess the current status of the Sal Forests in the *Rangpur* Division of Bangladesh. The study also aimed to identify the major forms of human disturbance, to assess the effects of disturbance on biodiversity and to recommend sustainable management strategies. It was found that the remnants are primarily concentrated in areas like *Mithapukur Upazila* of *Rangpur* district. In the *Naogaon* district, a few patches still occur in *Paikbhanda*, *Dhamourhat* and *Patnitolla* along the western border of the country. There is no Sal stands *Patnitolla*, which was converted into exotic woodlots. The *Shorea robusta* was the dominant tree species in the other remnants. Illegal logging, agricultural encroachment, and insect infestations were identified as existential threats to biodiversity. In the core and buffer zones of each forest natural regeneration should be facilitated to maintain the ecological balance and to ensure continuous forest coverage. In addition, direct seeding in the buffer zone and degraded forest areas can improve the naturalness. Advanced regeneration of rare or endangered species can protect the species from extinction. Very fast-growing and timbering native species should be planted in the encroached areas.

Keywords: *Altadighi* National Park, extinction, species decline, soil degradation, flora, fauna

Introduction

The Sal forests of Bangladesh are among the country's most important tropical deciduous forest ecosystems [1, 2, 3, and 4]. The forests grow on upland terrace soils, which are typically deep red-brown or shallow red-brown [1]. These soils are characterized by moderate to strong acidity, low organic matter and low fertility [1]. A "honeycomb" landscape pattern where forest patches are fragmented by low-lying depressions used for paddy cultivation [5]. Sal forests are dominated by *Shorea robusta* and support numerous plant and animal species [6]. However, anthropogenic disturbance has become a major ecological threat throughout Bangladesh's Sal forest belt [7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, and 13]. The disturbance gradients strongly reduce species richness and forest regeneration [14, 15].

The Sal forests of *Rangpur* Division represent a critical but highly fragmented part of the northern moist deciduous forest ecosystem in Bangladesh. In *Rangpur* district, the remnants are primarily concentrated in areas like *Mithapukur Upazila* [16]. In the *Naogaon* district, a few patches still occur in *Paikbhanda*, *Dhamoirhat* and *Patnitolla* along the western border of the country [1]. In the last inventory, these areas covered 3410 acres of natural Sal forest stands [17]. The *Dhamoirhat* Sal forests represent some of the most ecologically significant yet threatened moist deciduous patches in the Northwestern *Barind* Tract of Bangladesh. Unlike the central Sal forests, the *Dhamoirhat* patches, specifically those around *Altadighi* National Park, have undergone a radical transformation between 2024 and 2026 as part of a major restoration effort. These forest areas face extreme anthropogenic pressure, leading to significant habitat loss. The major objectives of this research are to identify the major forms of human disturbance in the Sal forests of *Rangpur* Division; to assess the effects of disturbance on biodiversity; to examine the socio-economic causes behind forest degradation; and to recommend conservation and sustainable management strategies.

Methodology

Both primary and secondary data were used for this study. The literature on the biodiversity of Sal Forests in the *Rangpur* Division was reviewed. The research articles, books, magazines, and newspapers were read to collect secondary data.

The secondary data were also collected from the Forest Headquarters of *Rangpur* Division. Field surveys were done to collect primary data. A total of 100 local people were personally interviewed to identify the threats. A total of 10 key informants were interviewed to understand the deeply rooted causes. Content analysis was done to interpret the data.

Biodiversity

Floral Diversity

Vegetation type	Name of the area			
	<i>Mithapukur</i>	<i>Paikbandha</i>	<i>Dhamoirhat/Altadighi</i>	<i>Patnitalla</i>
Tree	The Sal is the dominant species followed by Koroï (<i>Albizia procera</i>), Shimul (<i>Bombax ceiba</i>), Neem (<i>Azadirachta indica</i>), Sonalu (<i>Cassia fistula</i>), Jarul (<i>Lagerstroemia speciosa</i>)	<i>Shorea robusta</i> (Sal) remains the dominant species, followed by <i>Terminalia arjuna</i> (Arjun), <i>Phyllanthus emblica</i> (Amloki), and <i>Terminalia bellirica</i> (Bohera).	<i>Shorea robusta</i> (Sal) is the dominant species, followed by <i>Terminalia arjuna</i> (Arjun), <i>Lagerstroemia speciosa</i> (Jarul), and <i>Albizia lebbek</i> (Shiris).	<i>Eucalyptus camaldulensis</i> (Eucalyptus) and <i>Acacia auriculiformis</i> (Akashmoni) are the dominant species. <i>Shorea robusta</i> (Sal) is very rare.
Undergrowth	The forest floor is rich in traditional medicinal plants, including: Haritaki (<i>Terminalia chebula</i>) and Bahera (<i>Terminalia bellirica</i>). Shatavari (<i>Asparagus racemosus</i>), wild ginger and various ferns.	The understory traditionally hosts medicinal plants like <i>Andrographis paniculata</i> (Kalmegh)	The understory traditionally hosts medicinal plants like <i>Andrographis paniculata</i> (Kalmegh) and <i>Rauvolfia serpentina</i> (Sarpagandha). Several mushroom species are available here.	Not available

The biodiversity of these forests was dominated by the Sal tree (*Shorea robusta*), which typically constituted 70% to 75% of the canopy (Malaker et al., 2008). Common associates included *Lagerstroemia flosreginae*, *Gmelina arborea*, *Terminalia belerica*, and *Phyllanthus emblica* [17]. These forests were rich in medicinal flora such as *Terminalia chebula* (Hartaki), *Terminalia arjuna* (Arjune), and *Holarrhena antidysentrica* (Kurchi) [18]. The ecosystem supports

hundreds of undergrowth species, including various herbs, shrubs, and climbers like *Dioscorea* and *Spatholobus roxburghii* [17]. Another study identified 22 species of woody *macrofungi* in this region (including *Ganoderma* and *Trametes*), which are critical for wood decay and nutrient recycling in the Sal ecosystem [19].

The most notable event in this region has been the controversial “Restoration and Conservation of Biodiversity of *Altadighi* National Park” project. In 2024, the Forest Department cut down over 1,100 trees (primarily Eucalyptus and Acacia) that were part of older social forestry “woodlot” gardens. While this caused temporary public outcry due to the loss of shade, the objective was to remove “invasive” water-intensive species [20]. A core part of the project includes “Enrichment Plantations” on 20 hectares specifically designed to restore the natural Sal forest structure.

Faunal Diversity

The forest exists in small, isolated islands, which prevents the movement of mammals such as the Jungle Cat (*Felis chaus*) and the Golden Jackal (*Canis aureus*). Small Indian Mongooses, Jungle Cats, and occasionally Fishing Cats were rarely spotted near water bodies. Various species of Bats and Rodents (like the Indian Crested Porcupine) are occasionally visible. The bird species included Black *Drongos*, Oriental Magpie-Robins, Common *Mynas*, Black-hooded Orioles, Coppersmith Barbets, Black Kites and *Shikras*. Monitor Lizards are the largest reptiles present. Various snakes, including Garden Snakes and the Common Cobra, were found rarely. Common toads and bullfrogs inhabit the damp forest floor. The water inhabited Catfish, Snakeheads (*Shol/Taki*), and Eels (*Baim*).

The broader Sal forest ecosystem is historically known to support a diverse range of animals [21, 22, 23, and 24]. However, many larger mammals like tigers and elephants have been extirpated from these regions due to habitat loss [25]. *Altadighi* Lake, which is roughly 1km long, was re-excavated to restore water levels that had dropped below one foot, aiming to attract back the migratory birds that historically used the park as a sanctuary.

Conservation Threats

Illegal Logging: Historically, these forests have been exploited for timber, fuel wood, bark tannin, and native medicines. However, increasing population

pressure has led to “illicit felling” that continues despite legal moratoriums. Continuous tree removal reduces canopy cover and weakens forest structure. Consequently, the forests are broken by a “honeycomb” network of depressions used for paddy cultivation, making boundary maintenance extremely difficult. Forest fragmentation isolates wildlife populations and disrupts ecological connectivity. The forest no longer exists as a continuous block but rather as isolated “islands” of trees, which limits the movement of local fauna and reduces genetic diversity [29].

Agricultural Encroachment: Forest land is converted into cropland and homestead areas. Expansion of cultivation fragments the forest and destroys wildlife habitat. The forest is heavily “honeycombed” with settlements. Proximity to roads and villages is a primary predictor of low species richness. Continuous removal of leaf litter prevents the formation of humus, which is vital for the survival of the forest’s delicate herb and shrub layers. High grazing intensity from local livestock often destroys Sal seedlings before they can reach the “sapling” stage (stems >1 cm DBH). Domestic cattle grazing inside forests suppresses natural regeneration by trampling seedlings and compacting soil: The plantation of pineapple, banana, and rubber is a leading cause of land conversion. The use of pesticides and hormones in forest-adjacent farms has poisoned water sources and degraded forest soil. For the continuous harvesting of fuelwood and deadwood, the bird species are decreasing [28]. The collection of fuel wood and leaf litter by residents prevents the formation of a healthy humus layer, which is essential for seed germination.

Exotic plantation: The introduction of exotic species and rubber monoculture has reduced natural plant richness. The expansion of commercial fuel-wood plantations has rapidly exhausted natural forest stocks. The natural biodiversity is being replaced by commercial fuel-wood and rubber monocultures. In the northern mainland areas of *Rangpur* and *Dinajpur*, exotic species like Eucalyptus (e.g., *Eucalyptus camaldulensis*) are commonly favoured for timber, which can suppress native undergrowth and alter the original forest structure [26, 27]

Natural Threats: Insect infestations, such as the Sal borer (*Hoplocerambix spinicornis*), cause “die-back” in trees, leading to significant regeneration failure. Seedlings are frequently attacked by nematodes and root borers (e.g., *Pammene theristhis*), which significantly hinders the natural regeneration of the forest. Fungi such as *Cylindrocladium floridanum* and *C. scoparium* cause leaf spots and blight in *Shorea robusta*, further weakening the forest’s health.

Recommendations

Natural succession in the denuded core zone

Following the human disturbances, the successional species start to establish in the open areas under full sunlight. Eventually, in the absence of further disturbance, they occupy the site through a series of successional stages, leading ultimately to a plant community comprised of climax species. The denuded areas belonging to the core zone of our natural forests can be reforested through natural succession. However, during the early successional stage, natural regeneration requires protection from further anthropogenic disturbances.

Natural regeneration in the natural habitat

Natural regeneration is an effective means of regenerating the forest when conditions are right. It is usually favourable for the trees suited to the site. Effective natural regeneration from seed depends on seed productivity and dispersal. Alternatively, some species can regenerate from suckers and shoots. Sal (*Shorea robusta*) can effectively regenerate naturally from shoots even after a clear-cut harvest. Through natural regeneration, there is a higher probability of developing mixed stands. This may occur even when the original stand is pure. In the core and buffer zones of each forest, natural regeneration should be facilitated to maintain the ecological balance and to ensure continuous forest coverage.

Direct seeding in the peripheral zone

Direct seeding is usually carried out from the ground on sites that have been prepared for seed germination. While it is a more expensive procedure than natural regeneration, there is a greater likelihood of establishing the desired species. Large volumes of seed (5–10 seeds for each seedling) are required for

successful regeneration. The respondents stressed direct seeding in the buffer zone and degraded forest areas.

Gap-filling by rare species

In forests where small-scale disturbances exist, stand dynamics are controlled by the creation of gaps due to single or multiple overstory-tree mortality. Sometimes openings are created due to illegal logging on a small scale. Newly established seedlings or advanced regeneration of rare or endangered species should be recruited in these openings. This will protect the rare and very rare species from extinction as well.

Establishing terrestrial connectivity and a corridor

The fragments or remnants of the natural forests of Bangladesh maintain connectivity with the neighbouring fragments through the matrix. The level of biodiversity is influenced by the patches' size, continuous vegetation cover, and connectivity. They also added that the matrix plays the role of a corridor for the movements of wild animals across the landscape. Matrix also influences the edge effects of forest fragments. The surrounding environments have extensive effects on vertebrate communities residing inside the forest fragments. The primary forest species can use a matrix for migration in the nearby bigger patches. Some primary-forest species can use matrix habitats for reproduction as well. The vulnerability of species in fragments depends on their ability to use a matrix. A threatened species of fragments may colonize the matrix. Scattered trees can act as a bridge between the patches.

Maintaining population dynamics and ecosystem functioning

A healthy matrix can save small populations, collapsed metapopulations and endangered individuals from the edge effects and extinction. It was noted that in Bangladesh, most of the natural forests are comprised of a mosaic of patches with various levels of degradation and compositional disparity. A matrix can influence the biodiversity patterns in the mosaics and the vegetation-wildlife relationship. The surrounding matrix can support the plant populations of the remnants by facilitating seed dispersion and acting as a temporary habitat. The matrix can provide food resources, resting sites, and even breeding areas to frugivores. Seeds

in unconnected patches suffer stronger predation than those located in connected patches. The seed recruitment rates are lower in unconnected patches, which can collapse natural regeneration.

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